

A CONSOLIDATION MODEL FOR POWDER IMPREGNATED COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

A consolidation model is proposed for powder impregnated composites. The applied pressure is considered composed of (1) resin pressure, (2) fibre bed elastic pressure and (3) capillary pressure. The resin pressure is obtained from a solution of the flow of resin along a channel formed by three parallel fibres. The model predicts the time evolution of the void volume fraction as a function of the applied pressure. The correlation with experimental data is good and microscopy observations support the assumption that the flow mainly occurs along the fibre axis.

Keywords: powder impregnation, thermoplastic, void volume fraction, FIT.

1. INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic matrices in composites have found an increasing interest in the last decade owing to a number of advantages over thermoset matrices. These include improved toughness and durability, easy storage and processing cycles which do not involve any chemical reactions. A major drawback, however, is the difficulty of impregnating fibrous reinforcements with melts generally having much higher viscosity than thermoset resins. Several impregnation processes have been developed where the resin is dispersed within the fibre bundles prior to melting, thereby reducing the necessary flow length for impregnation [1]. Among these, the powder impregnation appears to be a promising technique. Many experimental studies of the mechanical properties of powder impregnated laminates have been presented [1-3]. Iyer and Drzal [4] studied the physical mechanisms of the spreading of melted particles and Ye et al. [5] modelled the impregnation time of polypropylene-glass fibres FIT ("Fibres Imprégnées de Thermoplastique" [6]) considering the powder as "reduced void content between the fibers". The study presented here considers the particle flow as the major mechanism of impregnation of powder impregnated laminates.

The aim of this paper is to model the consolidation time of powder resin impregnated continuous fibre reinforced composites. The first part of the paper presents the derivation of a consolidation time equation. The results of the model are then compared to experimental measurements performed on compression moulded FIT laminates.

2. CONSOLIDATION MODEL

2.1. Geometry

As the resin melts, each particle forms a bridge between adjacent fibres. There will be a range of different types of such resin bridges whose geometries are determined by surface energy effects. In our model it is assumed that each bridge connects three fibres and has the geometry shown in Figure 1. During the impregnation process each resin bridge will spread along the fibres driven by the applied pressure and capillary forces, until all adjacent resin bridges meet. At this point, the void volume fraction vanishes.

Figure 1: Geometry of the channel considered for the model. The distance between two fibres is d , the axial distance to flow to achieve full consolidation, which is equal to half the distance between two drops, is L and half the initial length of the drop is l_0 .

2.2. Assumptions

1. The flow transverse to the fibres is considered negligible compared to the axial flow.
2. The centre of each drop is considered stationary and its volume constant.
3. All the drops have the same dimensions and are equidistant to each other.

2.3. Derivation of a consolidation time equation

The pressure P_a applied to the laminate will be resisted by three components: the capillary pressure P_c , the pressure in the flowing resin P_r and the elastic spring force P_{spring} , due to the compression of imperfectly aligned fibres which act like a non-linear spring,

$$P_a = (P_r + P_c)v_m + P_{spring} \quad (1)$$

The capillary pressure is defined as positive when it resists the flow. Its sign depends on the surface properties of the different components and is usually negative, in which case it enhances the flow. An expression in terms of our parameters has to be derived for the resin, capillary and spring pressure, respectively.

Resin pressure. The Navier Stokes equation, applied to the flow of a fluid through a cylindrical channel neglecting the extensional terms¹, is presented in Equation 2.

¹ The calculation has been made including the extensional terms, but the result was very similar to the simpler expression presented here.

$$\frac{dP}{dx} = -\frac{8\eta V}{r_h^2} \quad (2)$$

where V is the flow velocity along the fibre axis, η is the viscosity and dP/dx is the pressure drop along the fibre-axis. The radius of the cylinder is replaced by the hydraulic radius r_h , which varies during flow and is defined as the ratio between the cross-section and the wetted perimeter. The velocity field over the resin bridge can be determined assuming that if the fibres are parallel and no transverse flow occurs, then continuity dictates that $d^2V/dx^2=0$. It follows that V varies linearly with x . and since $V=0$ at $x=0$, then

$$V(x) = \frac{x}{l} \frac{dl}{dt}$$

where dl/dt is the velocity at the end of the drop, x the co-ordinate in the fibre axis and l half the drop length. Integration of Equation 2 shows that the axial resin pressure distribution is parabolic. The average pressure, P_r , over the melt bridge is therefore,

$$P_r = \frac{8\eta l}{3r_h^2} \frac{dl}{dt} \quad (3)$$

Capillary pressure can be defined as the difference of the surface energy per unit volume of the system before and after impregnation divided by the matrix volume fraction. The surface energy before impregnation is the sum of the surface energies of the matrix $\gamma_m A_m$ and the fibres $\gamma_f A_f$, where A is the surface area per unit volume, γ is the surface energy and the subscripts f and m refer to the fibre and matrix, respectively. The surface energy after full impregnation can be considered as equal to the fibre-matrix interface energy, $\gamma_{fm} A_f$, since the area of the free surface of the laminate is negligible compared to the total fibre surface area. The capillary pressure can therefore be expressed as

$$P_c = \frac{A_f(\gamma_{fm} - \gamma_f) - \gamma_m A_m}{v_{m1}}$$

where v_{m1} is the final matrix volume fraction. The surface area per unit volume for a cylindrical fibre is given by $A_f=2(1-v_{m1})/R_f$, and if the melted particles are considered spherical the resin surface area per unit volume can be expressed as $A_m=3v_{m1}/R_m$, where R is the radius of each component. Introducing the Young Equation,

$$\gamma_{fm} - \gamma_f = -\gamma_m \cos \theta$$

where θ is the contact angle between the fibre and the melt, finally allows the capillary pressure to be expressed as:

$$P_c = -\gamma_m \left[\frac{2(1-v_{m1})}{R_f v_{m1}} \cos \theta + \frac{3}{R_m} \right] \quad (4)$$

Spring pressure. An expression for P_{spring} was proposed by Gutowski [7-9], which in terms of our variables can be written as follows:

$$P_{spring} = A_s \frac{\sqrt{\frac{lv_{f1}}{v_{f0}v_{f1}l + v_{f0}v_{m1}L} - 1}}{\left(\sqrt{\frac{0.829(v_{f1}l + v_{m1}L)}{lv_{f1}} - 1}\right)^4} \quad (5)$$

where v_f and v_m are the fibre and matrix volume fraction and the subscripts 0 and 1 refer to the initial and final state respectively. The value of the constant A_s lies between 250 and 1500 Pa corresponding to well and poorly aligned carbon fibres, respectively [8].

Matrix volume fraction v_m at any instant during consolidation is given by

$$v_m = \frac{v_{m1}}{v_{f1} + \frac{L}{l}v_{m1}} \quad (6)$$

Hydraulic radius. With a few straight forward manipulations, the hydraulic radius can be expressed as

$$r_h = R_f \frac{L}{l} \frac{v_{m1}}{v_{f1}} \quad (7)$$

Flow distance to achieve full consolidation. By geometrical considerations of Figure 1, it is possible to express L as:

$$L = l_0 \left(1 + \frac{v_{a0}}{v_{m0}}\right)$$

Final Equations. Introducing Equations 1, 6 and 7 into Equation 3 and rearranging it to express the velocity of the drop front gives

$$\frac{dl}{dt} = \frac{3}{8\eta} \frac{v_{m1}^2}{v_{f1}^2} \frac{R_f^2 L^2}{l^3} \left[\left(P_a - P_{spring}\right) \left(\frac{v_{f1}}{v_{m1}} + \frac{L}{l}\right) - P_c \right] \quad (8)$$

This expression must be integrated numerically due to the complicated P_{spring} expression. In the special case where P_{spring} can be neglected (i.e. low fibre volume fraction or high applied pressure), Equation 8 can be analytically integrated to express the time necessary for the melt to flow over a distance l ,

$$t(l) = \frac{l^4}{4b} - \frac{al^3}{3b^2} + \frac{a^2}{b^5} \left[\frac{1}{2}(a+bl)^2 - 2a(a+bl) + a^2 \ln(a+bl) \right] + C \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where } a = \frac{3R_f^2 v_{m1}^2 L^3 P_a}{8\eta v_{f1}^2},$$

$$b = \frac{3R_f^2 v_{m1}^2 L^2 \left(P_a \frac{v_{f1}}{v_{m1}} - P_c\right)}{8\eta v_{f1}^2}$$

and C is a constant of integration defined by the boundary condition that at time $t = 0$, $l = l_0$. The time necessary for the laminate to reach a given void volume fraction can be followed by replacing l in Equation 8 or 9 by

$$l(v_v) = \frac{Lv_{m1}(1-v_v)}{1-v_{f1}(1-v_v)} \quad (10)$$

3. EXPERIMENTS

3.1. Material

The material used for the experiments is FIT [6] (Fibres Imprégnées de Thermoplastique) of PEEK-CF supplied by Porcher Textile (France). Fibre bundles (3000 fibres yarns) are mingled with very fine PEEK powder ($R_m \approx 14 \mu\text{m}$) and enclosed in a thin sheath of the same resin. The volume fraction of the different components, needed for the computations, was measured by dissolving the PEEK resin out of an unconsolidated FIT in a 50/50 (w/w) solution of 1,2-dichlorobenzene and 4-chlorophenol in a soxleth extractor and then weighing the remaining dry fibres. The result is 62 vol% of fibres and 38 vol% of matrix.

3.2. Fabrication of the laminates

Unidirectional laminates, each made of 8 plies, were consolidated in a $50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$ matched-die mould under different pressures. Each ply was made by winding FIT yarns around an 80 mm diameter cylinder, and welding the bundles together every 50 mm. The laminates were placed in the mould at 380°C and left 15 min to reach the desired temperature. Then pressure was applied for 15 min. The displacement of the mould was recorded as a function of time using an inductive displacement gauge.

3.3. Void volume fraction measurement

Since the area of the laminate is constant throughout the consolidation ($50 \times 50 \text{ mm}^2$), the void volume content $v_v(t)$ is directly related to the laminate thickness $h(t)$ through the equation

$$v_v(t) = \frac{(h(t)-h_1)}{(h_0-h_1)}(v_{v0} - v_{v1}) + v_{v1}$$

The final void volume fraction v_{v1} of each laminate was evaluated by a density measurement according to ASTM-792 (immersion technique), and the initial void volume fraction v_{v0} was estimated to 0.35.

4. RESULTS

The values of the input parameters needed for the computation are listed in Table 1. The radii of the fibres and matrix particles were determined by optical microscopy, the final volume fractions of both components were quantified as described in the section 3.1, the melt viscosity was evaluated through literature data and a value lying between the two boundaries set by Gutowski for well and poorly aligned carbon fibres [8] was chosen for the spring constant. The theoretical and experimental void volume fraction versus time are plotted in Figure 2 for applied pressures of 5 and 10 MPa, respectively. The solid line shows the full solution to Equation 8 and the dashed line shows the analytical solution, ignoring the spring pressure expressed by Equations 9 and 10. Figure 3 shows micro graphs of polished sections of the laminates consolidated at 5 MPa (Figure 3a, parallel to fibres) and 10 MPa (Figure 3b, perpendicular to fibres).

Table 1: Values of the input parameters used for the computation (Equations 8 and 9).

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Unit
Spring constant	A_s	250	Pa
Mechanical pressure	P_a	5 and 10	MPa
Fibre radius	R_f	3	μm
Matrix powder radius	R_m	14	μm
Final fibre vol. fraction	v_{fl}	0.65	-
Final matrix vol. fraction	v_{ml}	0.35	-
Melt viscosity	η	10^3	Pa s

Figure 2: Void volume fraction as a function of time of a PEEK-CF FIT 8-ply laminate consolidated at 380°C under an applied load of (a) 5 MPa and (b) 10 MPa. The solid lines are calculated by Equation 8, the dashed lines by Equation 9 and the circles are experimental data (see section 3.3).

Figure 3: Micro graphs of 8-ply laminates of PEEK-CF polished sections: (a) $P_a = 5$ MPa, parallel to fibres and (b) $P_a = 10$ MPa, perpendicular to fibres.

5. DISCUSSION

Figure 2 shows that the model predicts the experimental data well. The full solution to Equation 8 (solid line) and the closed-form solution ignoring the spring pressure (dashed line) are very similar at an applied pressure of 10 MPa (Figure 2b) and tend to diverge from each other at 5 MPa (Figure 2a). This shows that the spring pressure influence on impregnation time is important for low applied pressures but becomes negligible if the applied pressure is much larger than the spring pressure, $P_a \gg P_{spring}$, in which case the closed form solution (Equation 9) can be used. Considering the parameters listed in Table 1, the maximum spring pressure calculated with Equation 5 at final fibre volume fraction, $P_{spring}(v_{f1})$ equals 5.6 MPa. The laminate processed at 5 MPa shows indeed a final porosity of 1.5%, which is visible in the micro graph of Figure 3a.

The capillary pressure, calculated by Equation 4 is of the order of $-1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ MPa, i.e. two orders of magnitude smaller than the applied load and the spring pressure. This result was confirmed by Ahn et al. [10] who have experimentally investigated the capillary pressure in a fibre bed measuring a maximum value of $-3.7 \cdot 10^{-2}$ MPa. The surface energy properties will therefore not influence the kinetics of impregnation for large applied loads or high fibre contents, but may nonetheless be critical for the adhesion between the resin and the fibres [11, 12].

The minimum pressure to be applied to obtain a void free laminate is set by the condition that the average pressure in the resin bridge must be greater or equal to zero when the fibre volume fraction reaches its maximum value, v_{f1} , and can be found from Equation 1 by

$$P_a^{\min} = P_{spring}(v_{f1}) + P_c \cdot v_{m1} \equiv P_{spring}(v_{f1})$$

The individual fibre bundles are still visible on the cross-section of Figure 3b, suggesting that the impregnation mainly occurs by the flow of the melted particles, as assumed by the model, and not by percolation of the outer sheath towards the centre of the bundle. This observation is expected since the permeability along the fibre axis is greater than the transverse permeability. Figure 3a supports the assumption that the porosity is formed by the unclosed gap between two adjacent bridges as implied by Figure 1. It should be mentioned that these voids tend to be present where the fibres are the most poorly aligned. There the spring pressure is locally the highest, and therefore the pressure in the resin P_r the lowest, reducing the melt flow. If the pressure in the resin becomes zero the flow stops leaving a gap between the two drops.

6. CONCLUSION

A model has been developed to predict the consolidation time of a powder impregnated composite. It considers the flow of the melted particles along the fibre axis driven by the applied pressure and resisted by the elastic pressure of the compressed fibre bed.

The model shows a good correlation with the experimental data and the microscopy observation of the laminates supports the assumption that the melt flow mainly occurs along the fibre axis.

The main parameters controlling the impregnation rate are the volume fractions of the fibres and the matrix, respectively, the particle sizes, and the applied pressure.

The capillary pressure either enhances or prevents the flow depending on the surface properties of the components, but it has been shown that its influence on impregnation time can be neglected for sufficiently large applied pressures or high fibre contents.

The voids can be considered as unfilled gaps between two adjacent bridges due to a locally higher spring pressure.

The spring pressure of the compressed fibre bed depends on the alignment of the fibres and on their volume fraction in the laminate. Its value is of the order of 1-10 MPa for 50-70 vol% approximately aligned carbon fibres. This minimum applied pressure is therefore necessary to obtain a void-free laminate.

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FIT-PEEK-CF(+Ps=0).data2222

		PEEK-CF (FIT)	
Rf[μm]=	3	Pc[MPa]=	0.01801143
Rm[μm]=	15	do=	50.1410186
vf1 =	0.65	.====> do/2=	25.0705093
vm1=	0.35	X=	3538.80257
η[Πα.σ]=	1000	a=	4.3366E+14
P[MPa]=	10	b=	2.2774E+11
γ[N/μ]=	0.04	cst=	1859.02537
θ[ραδ]=	0.5	vvo=	0.98002154
As[MPa]=	0.00025	vfo=	0.012986
		vmo=	0.00699246
		Ps (1)=	5.43